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Managing the difference between safety documentations and at-risk behaviors in the industry

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Abstract

Safety is in behavior, not in documents. An overemphasis on documentation may underemphasize safety in behaviors. A mismatch of HSE documentation with that of ground behaviors would raise many serious doubts. Of course, there are many reasons as to why the safety documentation and ground realities differ in behaviors among Indian organizations. Probably they do not know how to reduce at-risk behaviors and precisely that is why the incidents do not stop. But there are transformations in the attitudes of management and HSE professionals. This article presents the qualitative and quantitative results, discusses the implications, and provides experiential conclusions of 243 HSE professionals to improve safety culture as discussed in this article, to save people from injuries and fatalities. The conclusions for the difference between safety documentation and behavioral reality include shocking factors such as missing safety messages down the levels, safety documentation to make authorities happy, poor adherence to documentation requirements, compromising risk is a regular practice, no review of unsafe behaviors for corrective action, fast businesses delivering incidents, only behavioral awareness program, not planned intervention, and not focusing on the antecedents of safe/unsafe behaviors. Recommendations are reflected for managing the difference between safety documentation and at-risk behaviors in organizations.

1. INTRODUCTION

Safety documentation in the industry is carried out practically more for fulfilling the purpose of audits, awards, and business profits, and less for an intention towards implementation of safety culture. If people feel safe and secure, they could perform better in higher standards for their companies. In developed countries, all work areas: industries, offices, universities, medical institutions, Government, and social organizations adhere to the environment, Health, and Safety (EHS) standards. But in India, an estimated 82 percent of workplaces do not comply with EHS norms, according to a

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cross-sector survey by research and consulting firm Kaybase. There is, however, a growing consciousness of the need to comply with such safety requirements (Rao, 2019).

The purpose of the Indian National Policy on Safety, Health, and Environment at Workplace is to establish a preventive safety and health culture in the country through the elimination of the incidents of work-related injuries, diseases, fatalities, disasters and to enhance the well-being of employees in all the sectors of economic activity in the country (DGFASLI, 2021). But it is noticed that workplace safety managements remain fractured without the end-user involvement which is a serious gap between theory and practice at workplace orientations (Kristen and Alicia, 2020).

It is well said that if you have a will for safety culture, there is a way. According to International Labor Organization (ILO), each year 2.78 million workers die from occupational accidents and work-related diseases, and it is estimated that lost workdays globally represent almost 4 percent of the world's GDP (International Labor Office, 2019).

OSH Code 2020 prescribed duties of employees as follows, every employee at the workplace shall take reasonable care for the health and safety of themselves and other persons who may be affected by their acts or omissions at the workplace (India Briefing, 2021). Everyone deserves safety for life at work or otherwise, not necessarily by safety rules, regulations, or systems, but with the care and kindness of everyone around by adopting behavioral safety approaches to achieve an injury-free and zero-harm work life. The importance of leading Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) indicators in complementing lagging indicators is an emerging topic for the promotion of a prevention culture in organizations (Zwetsloot, 2020).

An unsafe behavior leads to incidents and will therefore impact the business and economy of the country. The absolute safety of people, society, and business lies in behavior, not the documents of safety. The documents are on the basis of one-time safety training which is 100 percent but behaviors on the ground remain unsafe as much as 30 percent (Kaila, 2020).

The safety professionals expressed that the difference between safety documentation and ground behavior of employees was because they are trained for safety but not for behavioral safety implementation. Also, because the safety culture leadership for human values such as active care, concern, affection, humility, humanity, equality, and compassion are not being exercised for the safety of colleagues as envisaged in ISO 45001 for managing internal risk control. This gap is not being addressed urgently by top leaders of the companies (Forum of Behavioral Safety, 2021).

2. RESEARCH QUESTIONS / OBJECTIVE STATEMENT

1. To study the factors as to why the safety documentation and ground realities differ in behaviors among Indian organizations.
2. To discuss its implications and provide conclusions to improve safety culture, to save people from injuries and fatalities.

3. METHODOLOGY

A total of 243 HSE professionals across Indian locations reflected their viewpoint on the difference between safety documentation and ground behaviors among organizations. Both primary and secondary data were collected from the study participants with diverse backgrounds of age, experience, designation, and education. Open-ended questions-based interviews and personal in-depth discussions with HSE professionals were conducted through remote data collection techniques over a period of 6-months (October 2020 - March 2021). Thematic analysis was performed.

Open-ended questions based on interviews and personal in-depth discussions with 250 HSE, medical, education, management, and mental health professionals were conducted through remote data collection techniques over 3 months (July-September 2020) in India from diverse locations and organizations. The responses of these professionals are presented in the following 10 themes.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS

The study participants were asked as to why safety documentation and ground realities differ in behaviors between Indian organizations and how this difference can be managed? Their responses were categorized on the eight themes below.

1. **Missing safety message down the levels**

Surprisingly, 90% of the study participants perceived that there was a lack of penetration of safety messages downstream. There prevails a Sab Chalta Hai (all is safe here!) Attitude by Management and Shop Floor People along with Enforcement Authority. In this cultural context, the Prime Minister emphasized that we needed to get moving from “chalta hai” to “badal sakta hai” which means a cultural change. It needs a people’s movement; the Government can at most be a catalyst (The Indian Express, 2017). Management must invest in frequent safety training and orientations to improve safety knowledge among workers (Suxia et al., 2020). Missing safety messages down the levels among all employees can be very risky as it is a major lagging indicator.

2. **Safety documentation to make authorities happy**

Almost 75% of the study participants expressed that to make regulators and statutory authorities happy, sometimes managements deceive themselves. This is salted Ahamkar tatva (ego-centric behaviors) of the company. Also, to fulfill statutory compliances, adequate resources are not provided by Indian organizations. That is why the ground reality, safety documentation, and behavior are different. This is one of the prime reasons for the lack of safety culture at workplaces. The accuracy of data documentation is still a major concern (El-Menyar, et al., 2016). If Safety documentation is done to make authorities happy, then the process of building a safety culture is surely hampered which can be very contrary to the business sustainability.

3. **Poor adherence to documentation requirements**

As many as 80% of the study participants believed that the lack of awareness regarding documentation requirements is a reason why the safety documentation differs from the ground reality. Also, they shared that accountability for adherence to documentation requirements is very poor. This research finding is a critical lagging factor for poor safety culture at Indian sites demonstrating an unsafe mindset. Documentation is one of the key areas to determine the standard of care that employees would receive for their health and safety (Mohd Aihatram Khan et al., 2020).

4. **Compromising risk is a regular practice**

As large as 76% of the study participants stated that compromising risk is an established practice for many Indian Organizations. This is a very serious finding of the study

indicating that at-risk behaviors are a regular affair at sites that would lead to incidents and accidents. A new study finds 73% of employees fear a return to the workplace will compromise personal health and safety (Business Wire, 2020). Compromising risk as a regular practice indicates a pathological and reactive safety culture which is extremely risky for the workforce as well as the businesses.

5. **No review of unsafe behaviors and corrective action**

About 85% of the study participants considered that there was a lack of review of individual unsafe behaviors and suitable CAPA. Corrective and preventive action (CAPA or simply corrective action) consists of improvements to an organization's processes taken to eliminate causes of non-conformities or other undesirable situations. This demonstrates a passive outlook towards the safety of the manpower at worksites. In companies with strong safety cultures, safety is embedded in daily management; it is part of the fabric of daily activity. It infuses every interaction, every decision, and every behavior (EHS Today, 2013).

6. **Fast businesses deliver incidents**

Nearly 85% of the study participants felt that fast businesses would not sustain with incidents. They further stated that the business leaders were more competitors which boils down to less leadership for the sustainability of the business. Competition is good only if it is not at the cost of safety and killing people for profits. Almost 30 percent of our industries and systems are non-compliant due to profit and production. A safety behavior survey was made as part of the safety performance measurements to identify at-risk behaviors for the industry (Government of Western Australia, 2021).

7. **Only Behavioral awareness program, not planned intervention**

About 78% of the study participants are of the view that many organizations are misguided by false thinking that BBS is just an awareness program, failing to understand that it is a planned intervention. They wish to control incidents by just an awareness program, they fail to do so, and incidents continue to take a toll on the human life and business of the company. Safety is a matter of time for spot correction. The human side of safety takes a backseat over the business targets and profits. All at-risk behaviors existed almost all the time, but they were not corrected, or they were delayed in spot correction. As per Santosh Srivastava, Chief Safety Officer of Cairn India, "thirty percent of global fatalities are from India, as safety is enforced most of the time, lacks management commitment, and not managed in the manner like production, cost, quality. Every cultural shift takes a minimum 2 years from reactive to interdependent safety culture." Hence, BBS focused on spot correction of all barriers and at-risk behaviors. BBS's motto is to increase the number of observers along with the increased quality of observations. On-the-spot correction together by all is live energy for organizations to excel. A behavioral safety program has limitations for its effectiveness if it is not conducted as a planned intervention on a regular basis.

8. Not focusing on the antecedents of safe/unsafe behaviors

Important focused group responses of the experienced HSE professionals are described below:

- Factory occupiers must take responsibility for change in the safety culture, which is missing.
- Sense of vulnerability should remain for not losing on safety actions.
- Managing heightened risk perception through ears and eyes during COVID-19 circumstances.
- Future of safety lies in how we are going to buy people into the humanistic process like empathizing intentions among employees to be framed as organizational planned intervention.
- Discussing/sharing what factors influence employees to do at-risk behaviors at the site or anywhere
- National framework on behavioral safety in industries would greatly impact safety cultures
- Benchmarking behavioral safety by national institutions to balance lagging/leading indicators

The above-stated responses necessitate focusing on the antecedents of safe/unsafe behaviors.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The major conclusions for the underlying difference between safety documentation and behavioral reality include the seven lagging factors for the safety cultures such as missing safety messages down the levels, safety documentation to make authorities happy, poor adherence to documentation requirements, compromising risk is a regular practice, no review of unsafe behaviors and corrective action, fast businesses deliver incidents, and only behavioral awareness program, not planned intervention. These are sufficient reasons to indicate that safety culture is lagging at many sites in Indian locations. This reveals that incidents might happen, and consequences can be catastrophic, which will cause potential loss of lives or severe injury, stop operation and non-productive time, undesirable cost and expenses, destruction of equipment and defame of company reputation (Mohammed Gehad et al., 2020).

Factors that are responsible for the difference between safety documentation and ground reality, include but are not limited to:

1. Missing safety messages down the levels.
2. Lacking safety documentation to make authorities happy.
3. Poor adherence to documentation requirements.
4. Compromising risk is a regular practice.
5. No review of unsafe behaviors for corrective action.
6. Only behavioral awareness programs but no planned intervention.
7. Poor focus on the antecedents of safe and unsafe behaviors.

The visible gaps between safety documentation and behaviors need to be addressed urgently by top leaders of companies described below as recommended by the study participants.

1. Behavioral Safety shall be the mandatory subject on every industrial safety curriculum. At least one hour of BBS training per month shall be given to all the employees of the company including contractors. BBS implementation shall be the agenda at board level discussion and mandatory for HSE Committee. The COVID-19 outbreak has changed the approach towards workplace safety. Although robust plant design, engineering controls, SOP, and OSH organizations are essential, they will be ineffective if behavioral safety aspects are not considered (Gabhane, 2020). Any small incident even a first aid injury would call for a review of the entire BBS management system, to locate and correct what is missing.
2. Indian experiences and best practices need to be documented. There is a lot of enthusiasm to adopt BBS for injury prevention amongst the industrial fraternity, to name a few i.e. DCM Shriram, Sembcorp, GAIL, SAIL, Tata Projects, IOCL, HPCL Academia is searching for ways and means to introduce BBS. Statutory Authorities are looking for a private partnership that has the capability to implement BBS. Government institutions like DGFASLI, NSC are keen to find how to take it to industry and encourage incident reduction. Huge potential available in the market to mentor/coach/train and to deliver BBS. Industry and academia have recognized BBS as an effective tool for intervention in safety management. Online sessions can be conducted for promoting BBS to increase networking and outreach to various industries and educational institutions.
3. Though we are successful in promoting BBS in various industries, the real need is to address this at schools and colleges if we really wish to see the change we want. This is part of CSR in various villages; most of the companies are doing awareness on the environment, road safety, and good health. BBS must be taken to the community, as road safety and social distancing, and personal hygiene is already being tracked in our BBS checklist.
 - We cannot be safe unless the community around us is safe.
 - BBS plays a vital role in building a positive safety culture.
 - BBS can be integrated from the workplace to any place.
 - Reward safe behaviors.
 - Promote safety learning from childhood.
 - Make safety a compulsory subject in all curriculums.
 - All-out support for BBS expressed by DGFASLI, NSC, and Director NITIE
 - BBS from the workplace to any place is possible. BBS can be applied anywhere.
4. Measurement matrix and maturity ladder of BBS program are very important to exercise. For implementing BBS, a sufficient time minimum of 2-3 years should be given to achieve a good result, normally managements think that it should happen in few months. Top management's involvement and support are crucial for program success.
5. India has a very vague safety culture. Negative reinforcement is required in the unorganized sector to make it a habit leading to positive reinforcement. Zero Accident Vision is possible, and it can be achieved by Behavior-Based Safety. Companies have realized the importance of BBS, which is not industry-specific and applicable to all sectors. BBS along with traditional safety systems, industries can dream of the vision of Zero Incidents/accidents. Behavioral intervention or BBS is most successful at the time when all employees in the organizations are thinking together about the concept of BBS, starting with the leadership and the last person at the site. Top leadership and all the rest thinking together about implementing BBS to save human life from an injury. At-risk behavior is an emergency for its spot correction and a

possible safe behavior for a safety culture. BBS should not rest in conversation rather get implemented. Total behavioral safety implementation for sites would require professional mentoring as well as doubt clarifying sessions. Progressive companies who have passion and innovation for safety are ready to enable their manpower for the BBS approach. If there is a will, it is possible to implement in big and widespread organizations also.

6. The Indian Industry lags in following safety protocols, and betterment can be achieved only if the people at work start understanding that their life is precious, and it is them individually who will lose if they don't remain safe. Understanding the importance of "Learning to Unlearn." There is a need to understand the importance of saying "no" to whoever if they feel that the work they have been assigned is not being carried out safely. A safety professional shared, "as a 4th Engineer, I have seen a Cadet dying in the Container because he wasn't properly equipped with PPE and was asked by his senior to go down, all he had to say was "No." Understanding that an accident does not ask if you are highly experienced or if you have a training certificate. It's you who have to take a call."
7. There is a need to use the leading and lagging indicators for rating BBS while implementing. It is well said by a safety officer, "being as a shop floor person (manufacturing/process unit) if the shop floor people are safe, then the organization is safe." To make them understand their safety, daily interaction/training/feedback is a must and make BBS a humanistic movement and emotionally connect people at the site in order to succeed fully.
8. Post-COVID, the workplace concept is changing. New concerns in safety, health, and psychosocial relations arise. BBS must transform to address such concerns. e. g. Ergonomics, workaholic culture. There is plenty of scope for MSME and the service sector to adopt BBS. The challenge would be to offer BBS to smaller groups or to even individuals. Post COVID-19, behavior-based-safety (BBS) became a more popular approach to safety management, which sees the main cause of accidents in unsafe behavior or act (Gabhane, 2020). How much value is being delivered by the BBS implementation is measured by the percentage of participation of observers. That is how many people are being observed and spot-corrected by each observer, divided by what was the goal of participation for observers in each department. BBS means an instant spot correction of at-risk behavior by everyone at the site; therefore, an observer is trained for a moment of correcting, and an organization is trained to sustain it. A leadership of dreams and determination can do it.
9. What is lacking in sites at the department level, is as follows:
 - Appreciation of BBS observers
 - Observer's positive approach of correction as big brother
 - Developing more observers
 - Making observation round daily
 - Goal setting by departments for a number of observations by each observer to calculate % of observer's participation
 - Alternatively, you may decide at the steering team for inclusion of observer name in the BBS checklist, for those who do at-risk behaviors repeatedly.
10. What is organizationally lacking somewhere is Humanistic Behaviorism and Mindfulness (Safety with Human touch & actively caring). We need to refresh people with these basic aspects of behavioral safety periodically. In this regard, a 10-point organizational BBS implementation commitment test for zero-harm actions (Kaila, 2020) is recommended:

- Has your CEO issued a circular to all employees for BBS implementation?
- Has your organization displayed BBS banners across all work areas?
- Has your organization formed the BBS steering team?
- Is the BBS steering team meeting every month and reviewing progress?
- Are all employees and workmen aware of the BBS concept of observations-spot-correction?
- Is the organization calculating and displaying the BBS scoreboard each month?
- Has the organization issued a BBS identity sticker to all observers to fix on the helmet?
- Do all HODs make BBS rounds each day?
- Has BBS implementation affected reduced incidents at sites?
- Has BBS implementation affected reduced barriers in safety?

11. Risk perception is important especially when we have low safety consciousness in the majority of the contract associates. Timely observation by employees is precious for someone to be saved from injuries. So, BBS is to be a part of the Risk Assessment and HAZOP study as an integral OHS management system. BBS means Better Business Sense.

To conclude, it is imperative that the safety documentation is in tandem with ground realities. Mismatch of HSE documentation with that of ground behaviors would raise many serious doubts about the compliances of safety rules and regulations on part of everyone concerned such as the company management, factory owner, auditors, safety department, factory inspectorates, etc. Finally, this hampers business sustainability and exposes manpower to risks as a threat to life. Hence, safety is to be implemented with an outlook of humanity and to be managed with humanistic philosophy more actively, it would save human beings from fatalities and business from losses. Needless to mention that the insurance, as well as enforcement agencies, take cognizance of this research and its implications for reinforcement of safety culture in workplace establishments.

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